

UNDERSTANDING EFFECT OF ARCTIC TEMPERATURE ON POST-IMPACT FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Composite sandwich, Impact, Post-impact bending, Flexural collapse modes, Arctic environment

ABSTRACT

This study analyses the post-impact bending behavior and underlying collapse modes of Divinycell H-100 PVC foam core with woven carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) face sheets composite sandwich panel. Effects of low temperature, face sheet thickness and impact energy on collapse modes in three-point bending have been predicted analytically and validated by experimental results. A series of low-velocity impact tests with 4 J and 8 J impact energy were performed by an Instron CEAST 9350 drop tower system at three different temperatures 23, -30 and -70 °C. Impacted specimens were then subjected to a three-point quasi-static bending test for identifying flexural collapse modes. Bending characteristics were analyzed on both sides of the specimens (front impact face and back distal face). Analytical results portray that indentation, core shear, face wrinkling are the main competing collapse modes. Results also elucidate that the competing flexural collapse mode strongly depends on pre-bend impact, face sheet thickness, temperature, and bending configuration. Experimental results are further compared and validated with analytical predictions. Experimental results show that thick specimens were collapsed either by indentation or core shear. However, thin specimens at 23 and -30 °C revealed a new mechanism of core tensile failure while debonding was observed at -70 °C. This new observation of core tensile failure is attributed to the reduced tensile properties of the back-face sheet. Collapse mode shows a strong dependence on the face sheet thickness, pre-existing damage, bending direction, and temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

The reduction in Arctic sea ice region over the last three decades has opened new sailing routes which are more efficient and economical. This has resulted in the increased use of marine and naval vessels in extremely low-temperature arctic conditions. The fundamental challenge of operating in such a cold and harsh environment lies in the understanding of how materials and structures behave and perform at extremely low temperature.

Structural sandwich composites have been widely used in many application areas such as aircraft structures, ship hulls, and wind turbine blades, bridge decks due to their superior bending stiffness, low weight, excellent thermal insulation, and acoustic damping. They are used in many engineering fields due to their superiority over the conventional structural constructions such as high bending stiffness and good weight saving. The behavior of sandwich beams depends on the properties of core material, especially under impact loading. They typically consist of two thin, stiff, and strong faces which are separated by a thick, light, and shear-resistant core. However, one of the major concerns in the use of sandwich composites such as in the conventional polymer matrix composites is the impact-induced damages which may occur during normal maintenance operations or during service conditions.

There are many studies regarding the impact and flexural properties of sandwich structures. Steeves and Fleck [1-2] studied the collapse mechanism of sandwich beams in three-point bending. However, the effects of temperature on the collapse mechanism need to be clarified. Sánchez-Sáez et al. [3] analyzed the dynamic flexural behavior of composite beams at low temperature. However, this paper investigates about composite laminates only. Caliskan and Apalak [4] evaluated low velocity bending

impact behavior of foam core sandwich beams. However, this paper has investigated bending impact behavior with respect to face sheet and foam core thickness, but it lacks the effect of low temperature on flexural behavior. Although Atas and Potoglu [5] examined the face sheet thickness influences over low-velocity impact response of sandwich beams with a foam core, the response needs to be studied over a range of temperature. Gustin *et al.* [6] examined impact, compression after impact, and tensile stiffness properties of carbon fiber and Kevlar sandwich composites for low-velocity impacts. They investigated impact parameters such as peak load, time to peak load, deflection at peak load, and absorbed energy. However, this paper has not explored the post-impact bending properties. Jiang *et al.* [7] studied the failure mechanisms of undamaged composite sandwich panels subjected to three-point bending. Still, the effects of pre-existing damage on the collapse mechanisms are needed to be explored extensively.

In this study, post-impact flexural properties of composite sandwich structures are analyzed both for bending inward and outward cases at room and low temperature. An analytical model is also developed to predict the collapse mechanisms of sandwich composite panels at different temperature. Analytical predictions are further compared and validated with experimental observations. The findings from this work will lead to a better understanding of the dynamic response and failure of composite sandwich structures at extremely low-temperature conditions, which will subsequently lead to an improved design for naval structures and materials that can operate safely and effectively in an arctic environment.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

The composite sandwich panel face sheets were constructed from $0^\circ/90^\circ$ woven carbon fiber and an epoxy matrix. Two different face sheet thickness combinations were used to make the composite sandwich samples. They were 0.25 mm and 0.75 mm thick face sheet separated by a 6.35 mm thick PVC foam core. The individual composite panel was cut into 150 mm x 100 mm size specimens. The post impacted sandwich samples were further cut into 150 mm x 25 mm bending specimen for a 3-point bending test.

Figure 1: Specimen (a) impact (b) three-point bending.

2.2 Impact and bending test

The impact tests were conducted using Instron CEAST 9350 drop tower with a 16 mm diameter hemispherical striker. The total mass of the impactor was of 3.48 kg and an environmental chamber was used for placing the specimen. Inside the environmental chamber, the samples were fully clamped. The drop height of the striker was used to control the impact energies. Each sample type was impacted at two different energy levels 4 J and 8 J. These values were chosen such that the low level caused minimal visible damage to the front face sheet, and the high level penetrated through the front

face sheet and into the core material. The samples were impacted at two different energy levels across three different temperatures: 23° C, -30° C, and -70° C. Thermostatic chamber was used to control the test environment temperature. The impact test setup is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Impact test with Instron CEAST 9350.

Bend tests after impact were conducted to test the residual strength and stiffness of the samples. A three-point bending apparatus was used following ASTM C 393 with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min Figure 3(a) and a span of 100 mm Figure 3(b). Samples were tested in bending at room temperature, -30° C and -70° C using an environmental chamber in Instron 5582 machine.

Figure 3: Three-point bending test with Instron 5582.

The impacted specimen is tested in a similar way as non-impacted (Figure 3(c) specimen that placed on a bending fixture. Bending configurations are obtained such that the impacted face sheet goes under compression (bending inward) as shown in Figure 3(d) and tension (bending outward) as shown in Figure 3(e). This orientation was chosen because depending on the real service support condition, the composite structure can bend in either concave or convex shape. For inward case, anvil touches the impacted zone (front face sheet) whereas, for the outward instance, it contacts the distal or back face sheet. In all trials, two specimens were tested under each condition.

2.3 Flexural collapse map construction

The composite sandwich panel usually shows four modes of collapse under three-point bending test as shown in Figure 4 [1-2]. It is worthy to be noted that the collapse means the initial failure of the composite sandwich panel under flexural loading. (Fig. 1) and a table (Table 1) are given below.

Figure 4: Collapse modes of composite sandwich under three-point bending.

Collapse modes are core shear, indentation, face wrinkling, and face yielding or micro-buckling. Corresponding critical collapse forces are calculated based on the following equations (1-4).

$$P_{cs} = 2bd\tau_c \quad (1)$$

where P_{cs} is the critical force for core shear, ' b ' is the sandwich width, ' d ' is the sum of core thickness and face sheet thickness, ' τ ' is the core shear strength and ' c ' is the sandwich core thickness.

$$P_i = bt_f \left(\frac{E_f \sigma_c^2 \pi^2 d}{3L} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where P_i is the critical force for indentation, ' t_f ' is the face sheet thickness, ' E_f ' is the face sheet elastic modulus, ' σ_c ' is the compressive strength of foam core, ' d ' is the sum of core thickness and face sheet thickness, ' L ' is the span of the beam.

$$P_{fw} = \frac{2bdt_f}{L} \sqrt[3]{E_f E_c G_c} \quad (3)$$

where P_{fw} is the critical force face wrinkling, ' E_c ' is the core elastic modulus, ' G_c ' is the core shear modulus.

$$P_{fy} = 4bdt_f \sigma_f / L \quad (4)$$

where P_{fy} is the critical force face yielding, ' σ_f ' denotes face sheet compressive strength.

The lowest among these competing forces prevails as the reason for the initial collapse. Equating each of two equations and considering the minimum force, collapse map was constructed for the geometrical dimensionless parameter of ' c/L ' vs. ' t/L '. Collapse forces were also predicted and compared to experimental values. Collapse maps in the 3-point bending test were constructed for three different temperatures. Room temperature properties are taken from [8],[9]. The values of different material properties [10], [11], [12] are listed in Table 1.

Temperature (°C)	E_f (GPa)	σ_f (MPa)	τ_c (MPa)	σ_c (MPa)	E_c (MPa)	G_c (MPa)
23	41.30	570.00	1.60	1.40	130.00	35.00
-30	42.54	535.80	2.00	1.61	143.00	40.25
-70	43.37	501.60	2.32	1.75	208.00	43.75

Table 1. Face sheet and core properties at different temperature.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Post-impact bending behavior

Three-point bending test results for undamaged thick specimens (0 J) and post-impacted (4 J and 8 J) are shown in Figure 5. The force-displacement curves for three-point bending are characterized by a linear elastic regime followed by a load drop. This load drop is recognized as the initial collapse or failure of the composite sandwich panel.

Figure 5: Experimental load-displacement plot for PVC foam-CFRP face sheet sandwich composite at (a) room temperature (b) -30 °C and (c) -70 °C.

At room temperature 23 °C (Figure 5 (a)), flexural load drop is gradual after the peak load, which indicates the plastic yielding of the specimen. This behavior is also seen at low temperature such as -30 °C (Figure 5 (b)), however, if the temperature drops to an extremely low temperature such as -70 °C impacted specimens with 4 J and 8 J reveals a sharp load drop immediately after the initial collapse or peak force (Figure 5 (c)). This interesting phenomenon is observed when the specimen bends outward. In other words, thick specimens break catastrophically for bending outward cases at -70 °C.

As the impact energy increases, flexural peak load decreases. This can be explained by the reduction in residual strength associated with the damage due to pre-bending impact. It is worthy of being noted that for a given condition namely 0 J, 4 J or 8 J pre-bend impact, peak force or flexural strength increases with the decrease in temperature. Bending outward cases offer superior flexural performance to bending inward cases. This behavior can be substantiated by the reduced compressive properties on the front face sheet during bending inward case due to prior impact, which severely damages the front face sheet matrix. Therefore, the front face sheet is no longer able to withstand sufficient compressive stresses during three-point bending. However, for bending outward case, the front face sheet is undamaged and can provide the required compressive properties during bending. In this case, the bottom face sheet which suffered impact damage still can provide sufficient tensile properties. The impact-induced damage on the bottom face sheet is typically confined to the matrix

where the fibers are not severely damaged. Therefore, bending outward cases offer sufficient compressive properties on front face sheet and tensile properties on the bottom face sheet that explain the superiority of bending outward to bending inward cases.

3.2 Collapse modes prediction at different temperatures

For constructing the flexural collapse maps at different temperatures, authors analyzed face sheet properties such as σ_f [13] and E_f [14] for non-impacted woven CFRP at -30 and -70 °C. Core properties such as E_c and σ_c at -30 °C and -70 °C [15] were obtained accordingly. By extrapolating and interpolating the results [16], Divinycell H100 PVC foam core properties namely G_c and τ_c were determined for -30 and -70 °C. These material properties at low temperature, along with room temperature properties, are shown in Figure 7(a). Except for σ_f , all other features increase with the decrease in temperature. Constructed collapse map for the composite sandwich beam across different temperatures is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Face sheet and core properties at different temperatures.

Using these properties, the collapse maps at 23, -30 and -70 °C are constructed as shown in Figure 7(a). For all experimental specimens (red pentagon and hexagon), the collapse mode predicted is indentation. Core shear area shrinks with the decrease in temperature at the expense of an increase in indentation and face wrinkling regime. Corresponding failure forces for collapse modes are shown in Figure 7(b).

Figure 7: Analytical prediction on (a) collapse modes (b) collapse forces during 3-point bending for PVC-CFRP composite sandwich panel.

As the temperature decreases, E_f , σ_c and τ_c increase. Required force for core shear at -30 and -70 °C (dashed blue and black lines with square markers) increases drastically compared to the indentation at the respective temperature (solid blue and black lines with diamond markers). As a result, core shear area decreases with the decrease in temperature (Figure 7(a)) which indicates core shear mode is less likely to prevail over other modes namely indentation or face wrinkling. Experimental failure loads are further superimposed on the analytically predicted forces at different temperatures. Predicted force lines (Figure 7(b)) slightly underpredicts for thin (pentagons) and overpredicts for the thick specimen (hexagons) at 23, -30 and -70 °C. Thus, predicted forces well agree with experimental values and substantiates the effectiveness of the constructed collapse map.

3.3 Effects of pre-bend impact energy on collapse modes

For better understanding, the effects of impact energy on flexural collapse, failure map for room temperature impacted specimen subjected to three-point bending (inward) was constructed (Figure 8(a)).

Figure 8: Effects of impact energy on (a) collapse modes during 3-point bending for PVC-CFRP composite sandwich panel and (b) collapse forces for bending inward at room temperature.

With an increase in pre-existing damage (4 J and 8 J impact), the indentation area broadens compared to the non-impacted specimen (solid green line with square marker). Thus, Indentation is the prevailing mode with the increased impact energy. Core shear mode is much favored for impacted

thick composite panel than a thin one since thicker and stronger face sheet prevents collapse through face sheet [17]. The experimental thin (green pentagon) and thick (purple hexagon) specimens are superimposed on the collapse map, and it is predicted that they will collapse by indentation. The associated collapse forces are shown in Figure 8(b). The limiting indentation force decreases with the increase in impact energy due to the impact-induced damage confined to the front face sheet. This explains the increased indentation area with an increase in impact energy (Figure 8(a)). Due to pre-bend impact, the top thin face sheet is much more damaged than that of thick for the same impact energy. Hence, with the decrease in face sheet thickness, the indentation area gets increased, whereas the core shear area decreases. Core shear mode is much favored for impacted thick composite panel than a thin one since thicker and stronger face sheet prevents collapse through face sheet. With the increase of impact energy, the intersection point between core shear and indentation lines tends to occur for a larger face sheet thickness. This means that for a given face sheet thickness the indentation will prevail for the higher pre-bend impact energy. Experimental collapse forces are superimposed again on the predicted force diagram. The analytical indentation lines (diamond marker) predict well for both 4 J and 8 J inward cases for the thin specimen, although it slightly overpredicts for the thick specimen.

3.4 Combined effects of temperature, impact energy and face sheet thickness

To understand the combined effects of face sheet thickness, pre-bending impact, temperature and bending configuration collapse map for the impacted thin specimen bending inwards at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are constructed as shown in Figure 9. Figure 9(a) shows that pre-bend impact energy influences the indentation-core shear transition line.

Figure 9: Collapse map for impacted specimen bending inwards for thin at (a) $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (b) $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

This line moves to the right downward as pre-bend impact energy increases, facilitating indentation. The decreased E_f due to front face sheet damage and subsequent core damage to some extent which degrades σ_c eventually lowers the limiting force required for indentation. As a result, the indentation area increases. Collapse map predicts that both thin (green pentagon) and thick (purple hexagon) specimens will fail through indentation.

However, thick specimen impacted by 8 J at $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ behaves differently compared to that at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ when bends inward (Figure 9(b)). It collapses by core shear (CS) whereas it collapses by the indentation in Figure 9(a). Inset experimental photo well validates core shear mode (red circles) in Figure 9(b). Hence, with the decrease in face sheet thickness, the indentation area gets increased, whereas the core shear area decreases. Core shear mode is much favored for impacted thick composite panel than a thin one since thicker and stronger face sheet prevents collapse through face sheet.

3.5 Novel and other collapse modes

Figure 10 shows the other modes namely core tensile and debonding those are observed particularly for the thin specimen.

Figure 10: Core tensile and debonding modes of the collapse of PVC-CFRP composite sandwich panel.

Core tensile failure which is a novel find by the authors is governed by a tensile crack that propagates through the core when thin specimen bends outward at room temperature. Debonding is observed when the interface of the PVC core and CFRP face sheet behaves as the weakest link during bending with 8 J impact on the thin specimen at extremely low temperature.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Composite sandwich structures with PVC foam core and CFRP face sheet having different thickness are tested under three-point bending. Post-impact bending behavior and collapse modes are analyzed experimentally and analytically. Collapse maps are constructed at different temperature for the non-impacted and impacted condition. Three basic failure modes, namely indentation, core shear, and face wrinkling, are distinguished analytically. The critical collapse forces are also computed and superimposed with experimental failure loads for validation. The analytical results are in good agreement with the experimental observation at different temperatures. Collapse mode shows a strong dependence on the face sheet thickness, pre-existing damage, bending direction, and temperature. Indentation is the dominant mechanism, whereas core shear, core tensile and debonding are also observed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the research grant N00014-18-1-2546 provided by the Office of Naval Research (ONR Program Manager: Dr. Yapa Rajapakse).

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